

THE IMPORTANCE OF POSITIVE RELATIONSHIPS IN THE FORMATION OF THE PERSONALITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, positive relations are described as an important tool in the formation of students' personalities, and a review of the literature on the topic, the content of educational and management skills, socio-pedagogical support of research activities, and the management of educational institutions that require consistent solutions. several problems are analyzed.*

Keywords: *positive attitude, confidence, responsibility, personal worldview, independence, practical skills, creativity, student personality formation.*

In the world education system, special attention is paid to pedagogical technologies that encourage the formation and development of the student's personality through works of art, familiarization with universal human values, appreciation of beauty and goodness, aesthetic taste and creative activity. In particular, a number of scientific researches are being carried out in the world to clarify the pedagogical possibilities of music and visual arts in the aesthetic education of elementary school students, to develop the aesthetic thinking of students through musical pedagogy and psychology. It is especially important to develop the aesthetic consciousness and worldview of elementary school students by teaching them to work with artistic texts, and to improve the mechanisms of developing children's aesthetic qualities. This, in turn, is an important tool in forming the personality of students.

Educational activities should create an opportunity for primary school students not only to develop cognitive processes at a high level, but also to develop positive attitude characteristics of these young people. During this period, the formation of the child's personality continues. A student's success at school is a completely positive basis for his further mental development and personality formation. As a result, it can be seen that the child begins to understand his place in his family, his class and other communities. Transition to a new activity creates a new attitude of the student to his main activity. A sense of positive attitude begins to grow in him. He understands that good behavior and character are necessary and that it is his duty, that the established rules and requirements must be followed. Feeling like a real student, he needs to be a good student. The moral consciousness of students of this age undergoes important changes during the 1st and 4th grades, and moral qualities, knowledge and imagination are significantly enriched, and the child begins to understand himself. Although he does not know his own good and bad qualities, he feels that he is "I". He realizes his duty, purpose, the need to fulfill it, and the fact that it is his duty to do homework and repeat. Elementary school students are interested in knowledge about many environmental phenomena and positive social relations that are not included in the school curriculum. These interests are also reflected in the child's interest in positive games, which are

often ignored. Such games reflect his social interests, emotions, concern for the team. Curiosity is a form of manifestation of broad mental activity of children of small school age. Openness, trustworthiness, willingness to fulfill all the tasks of the teacher are effective conditions for him to know the importance and importance of studying in order to become a person needed by the country.

Education and upbringing of young people in developed countries around the world is important attention is being paid and state programs in these areas are being adopted. In this regard, fundamental reforms are being carried out in the continuous education system in our republic, and their essence is to solve the issues of raising the young generation, who are our future, to be intellectually capable, spiritually mature, physically strong, and innovatively developed well-rounded individuals. The results achieved in them are small. It is an important didactic basis for raising the thinking scope of school-aged students, through which the content of primary education is formed based on modern requirements. At the same time, the level of development of society requires the use of advanced achievements of science and technology in modern education. The results of our research on the development of creative activity among elementary school students have developed innovative methods and technologies for the implementation of a certain educational direction in the teaching of certain subjects in the educational process, and a certain way from them. It shows that it is necessary to optimally organize primary education by creating an environment of creative activity intended for effective use in the fields.

In addition, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 on the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan has created ample opportunities to solve the problem under consideration. Also, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 17, 2018 on the State program "Youth is our future" "educating young people is the most important condition for stable and rapid development of the country". Accordingly, work in our society is a real source of creativity and joy. Primary school students should be encouraged to have a creative attitude to academic work and help to turn work into a real source of creativity and joy. Mental arithmetic is a mandatory condition and component of teaching, educating and developing creative activity of elementary school students at the primary stage of the general education school. In addition, various methods of elementary school students are implemented through extracurricular activities. Famous scientists N.K. Krupskaya, A.S. Makarenko, A.V. Lunacharsky, S.L. Rubinshteyn believe that the science of labor or technology occupies an important place in the development of creative activity of elementary school students. The purpose of mental arithmetic is to educate the personality of primary school students along with forming their creative activity.

Elementary school students develop a sense of caution and memory by making and preparing something with their own hands, as well as teach responsibility, perseverance and patience. All of these will not only help elementary school students learn to write graphic essays in school, but these skills will be useful and effective later in their lives. Technology classes creative activities of primary school students It helps to develop imagination and thinking in the formation of art and art. In addition, it is a sensitive tool that is very important for children with cerebral hemisphere diseases and speech disorders of elementary school students.

Creative or master classes are not only for elementary school students helps in developing imagination, but also in the formation of many practical skills. For example, sewing a button, making something out of colored paper, preparing breakfast, making gifts for your family and

friends with your own hands, all these things should be developed in elementary school students. And more. one important aspect is that: through the ability to make an object, creativity, the elementary school allows the student to be more confident about himself, to get rid of the feeling of not being able to enter the world of adults around him without the support of adults. will do. But self-confidence, confidence in one's abilities, elementary school creates necessary conditions for a student to be truly happy. Work is a process that directs elementary school students to creative activity by making an object through various materials, in which it is useful and aesthetic to decorate during their life (games, work, leisure). creates meaningful things and products.

It is known that interest is the attitude and direction of choosing an object, an activity, which is the emotional decoration of students. Accordingly, in psychology, two types of interest are identified in the educational process of students: the first is direct interest, and the second is indirect interest. Every teacher tries to create indirect interest in his subject in his students. Pupils show an active attitude to education through interests. Of course, there are several factors and effective methods for developing primary school students' interests and creative activities through interest, and we will consider a few of them.

The "closed book" method is one of the methods of using text material in a specific subject, which requires students to remember the information contained in the text, but not to repeat the text during the discussion. This method also needs to be used in combination with other methods and students should not limit themselves to "retelling" in reading.

This method is very useful in summarizing lessons (interactive learning sessions) in the environment of creative activities of primary school students. It is the most convenient and which is easy to process) helps to form the creative qualities of a person, but is of general importance. These lessons develop the mental abilities of primary school students, expand their worldviews and imaginations, form moral ideas and help to form a creative attitude to the world around them. In addition, all products made of clay (plasticine) have a great influence on the decorative and practical art of the joys associated with life. The material is paper. Production of paper products helps the development of muscles, improves the visual activity of students, prepares them for the development of writing skills, the aesthetic development of elementary school students, they also rely on their intelligence in matching colors to each other. Especially clay (plasticine) lessons - (sculpture) or making something using clay plasticine. Sculpting lessons help to form the creative qualities of a person, which are not unique (necessary for this and similar work) for elementary school students, but is of general importance. These lessons are mental for elementary school students develops their abilities, expands their outlook, imagination, forms moral ideas and helps to form a creative attitude to the surrounding world. In addition, all products made of clay (plasticine) have a great influence on the decorative and practical art of life-related joys.

Also, the formation of responsibility in elementary school students is related to the development of their voluntary attention and the formation of strong willed efforts to overcome difficulties in completing tasks in the process of acquiring knowledge. elementary school students are dominated by involuntary attention, and it is difficult for them to focus on the perception of "non-interesting" material, so teachers should use various pedagogical methods and teaching tools that help students to be interested in learning. At the same time, it should be taken into account that in addition to external entertainment, the studied material should be interesting for students, and the student's knowledge of the content of the studied topic and the emergence of interest. the level of students' understanding of educational tasks at school. Man, especially during the age of

technology, tried to subjugate nature, sometimes having many negative effects on it and completely changing it.

Changes in the Earth's surface, climate, flora and fauna, and biosphere in the 20th century are a vivid example of this. After all, "...nature has suffered greatly due to the actions and blind actions of man without thinking about the future" 2. For elementary school students, the teacher's instructions, advice and requirements are of particular importance, because imperative (imperative) elements prevail in their moral consciousness, so they consciously fulfill these requirements of the teacher, and this affects the formation of ideas about norms. The behaviors and activities that each student considers when evaluating their own behavior and the behavior of their classmates. One of the characteristics of the formation of responsibility in elementary school students is that the personal example of parents and teachers is of great importance for educating them as a personal quality of responsibility. Therefore, adults should have personal responsibility, society should show examples of responsible behavior in the case of putting other people's interests above their own. And then, in the student's elementary school, the value of responsibility gradually takes the leading place in the moral consciousness of behavior.

Suggestions and recommendations. The school is aimed at perfect development of the person, identification and development of creative abilities of the growing generation, as well as rational use of their free time. Because the school is a component of the continuous education system, its main task is to provide education and training to young students, while forming the student's personality, to spend their free time outside of school and class, is to inculcate the national idea and patriotism in his mind.

Thus, the following features should be taken into account when forming the student's personality in primary grades through positive relationships, and forming responsibility in students:

- Primary school students have involuntary attention and it is difficult for them to focus on the perception of "non-interesting" material, so teachers should use various pedagogical methods and teaching tools that help to arouse students' interest in learning.

- the formation of a sense of responsibility in elementary school students in extracurricular activities should be carried out on the basis of cognitive, emotional-value and behavioral components.

It is important to create a situation of choice and make one's own decision in forming a person and forming a responsible attitude.

REFERENCES

1. Mamajonova Shoxista Kamoldinovna "BOSHLANG'ICH SINI O'QUVCHILARIDA IJOBIY MUNOSABAT USULLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISH " ISSN 2181-1717 (E) Образование и инновационные исследования (2022 год №12) <http://interscience.uz> 333
2. Rayimova Gulmira Toshtemirovna, & Marifat Butayorova. (2022). METHODOLOGICAL BASES FOR THE USE OF MODERN TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE LESSONS OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE IN PRIMARY GRADES. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(11), 88–91. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijp/Volume02Issue11-15>
3. qizi, B. M. X. . (2023). Opportunities for the Formation of Mental Thinking of Students on the Basis of Gender Equality and Differences. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on*

- Innovative Education*, 2(4), 114–116. Retrieved from <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/semantic/article/view/1003>
4. Ollokulova F. U. Value relationships in young people and the uniqueness of their decision making //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 9. – С. 373-376.
 5. Olloqulova F. U. TADQIQOTCHILIK FAOLIYATINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK TAVSIFI. *Tadqiqotlar*, 6 (2), 336–339. – 2023.
 6. Burkhanov A., Avlaev O., Abdusalilova Sh. Responsibility as a criterion for determining personal maturity/ E3S Web of Conferences 2021
 7. Оллокулова Ф. Boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarida tadqiqotchilik faoliyatini konsentrizm asosida shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-pedagogik ahamiyati //Общество и инновации. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 10/S. – С. 128-134.